

PURE MOMENT APPROACH TO DETERMINE MIXED-MODE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF SANDWICH FACE/CORE INTERFACES

C. Berggreen^{1*}, G. A. Kardomateas² and L. A. Carlsson³

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark,

²School of Aerospace Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, USA,

³Department of Ocean and Mechanical Engineering, Florida Atlantic University, Boca Raton, USA

* Corresponding author (cbe@mek.dtu.dk)

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Abstract

Closed form algebraic expressions for stress intensity factors, energy release rate, and mode-mixity phase angle of debonded sandwich specimens have been applied to a recently developed test method called DCB-UBM. In this method a sandwich specimen with a face/core interface crack is subjected to edgewise moments until the crack propagates. A special test fixture has been developed which allows fracture testing over a full range of positive and negative mode-mixity phase angles. The mode-mixity phase angle for sandwich specimens with a soft and rigid core is calculated as a function of the ratio between the edge moments applied to the DCB-UBM specimen.

1 Introduction

One failure mode which is of particular concern in sandwich panels is that of face/core debonding. Typical sandwich panels consist of a polymer or metal foam core sandwiched between stiff composite or metal face sheets. The bond between such highly dissimilar materials is often a weak link, and in several occasions, face/core debonding have been the reason for structural collapse. The debonds may be caused by poor manufacturing procedures resulting in a poor face/core interface, or out-of-plane loads such as hard object impact loads, slamming events, bird strikes etc.. As a consequence, extensive research has been dedicated measuring debonding under peel ("mode I") and shear ("mode II") conditions. It should be pointed out that the issue of mode I and mode II is not as clear for a face/core interface crack as for a crack in a

homogenous material, because the strong mismatch of material properties across the interface corrupts the traditional physical understanding of the mode I and II mechanisms, see the review by Hutchinson and Suo [1].

Mixed mode testing of sandwich specimens has been approached using the mixed mode bending (MMB) sandwich specimen [2] and a double cantilever beam (DCB) test, where unequal moment couples are applied to the arms of the debonded region of the specimen [3,4]. This method is called DCB-UBM, where UBM abbreviates "uneven bending moments". The MMB specimen is loaded by transverse forces at the center and at the ends of the debonded end regions. Although this specimen has been tremendously successful, especially for monolithic composites, it suffers from two major disadvantages when applied to sandwich specimens; i) the specimen is essentially limited to negative mode-mixity phase angles, and ii) the transverse shear forces will cause crack tip rotation strongly influenced by the material combination and test configuration. This factor has been examined for layered isotropic materials by Li et al. [5].

For the DCB-UBM specimen, however, only pure end moment couples are applied making analysis of the specimen much more straight-forward. This was the subject of a recent paper by the current authors [6]. In this analysis closed-form expressions for the energy release rate and mode-mixity phase angle were derived for a debonded sandwich beam. This analysis extends the formulas in the literature for a delamination in a homogeneous composite [7] and an interface crack in a bi-material [8].

In this study, we will examine the range of mode mixities possible with the DCB-UBM test method.

This will be accomplished applying the previously mentioned analysis of a debonded sandwich specimen loaded by end moments only. The results from the analytic model and its relevance for DCB-UBM testing will be demonstrated for sandwich specimens with aluminum face sheets and two types of foam core materials.

2 Analysis

The most general case of an “asymmetric” sandwich is considered, i.e. the bottom face sheet not necessarily of the same material or thickness as the top face sheet. The energy release rate is obtained by use of the J-integral and the expression is derived in terms of the forces and moments at the debond section. Figure 1a shows an element of the sandwich beam containing a debond crack at the face/core interface. The debonded face sheet layer behind the crack tip carries a compressive axial force P_d and bending moment M_d . The lower sections containing the core and lower face is subjected to a compressive force, P_s , and moment M_s . The forces and moments are assumed to act at the neutral axes (NA) of the top layer and lower sections (debonded part and substrate), see Fig. 1. On the right cross section ahead of the crack (base) a compressive force, P_b , and a moment, M_b , are acting, again at the neutral axis of the intact part of the sandwich beam section. The forces and moments are per unit width (b) of the beam.

In our previous study [6] we extended the approach by Suo and Hutchinson [7], who analyzed a bimaterial structure, to a “trimaterial problem”, i.e. a sandwich structure with a face/core interface crack. Closed form expressions of the energy release rate and mode-mixity phase angle were derived.

With reference to the DCB-UBM specimen [3,4] we intend to apply the closed form expressions to our experimental work. The basic principle of this test method is shown in Fig. 2. A flexible wire, anchored at a point, is drawn around a pulley mechanism as shown in Fig. 2. By applying force, F , to the other end of the wire, moments M_1 and M_2 are introduced through the two arms, adhesively bonded to the cracked end of the DCB specimen,

$$M_1 = Fl_1 \quad (1a)$$

$$M_2 = Fl_2 \quad (1b)$$

where, the lengths l_1 and l_2 , and the signs of the moments are defined in Fig. 2. It is possible to rearrange the wires to change the direction of the applied moments, and their magnitude may be changed by changing the lengths, l_1 and l_2 . Hence, this test principle produces pure moment loading on the delaminated end of the sandwich beam. With reference to the general loading shown in Fig. 1, we obtain,

$$P_d = P_s = P_b = 0 \quad (2a)$$

$$M_d = M_1, \quad M_s = -M_2, \quad M_b = M_d + M_s \quad (2b)$$

Hence, the loading configuration is reduced to the one shown in Fig. 3. The energy release rate for plane strain ($\epsilon_z=0$) is given by

$$G = \frac{1-\nu_{f1}^2}{2E_{f1}} \left(\frac{P^{*2}}{h_{f1}} + E_{f1}^2 \frac{M_d^{*2} h_{f1}^3}{D_d^2 12} \right) + \left(\frac{P^{*2}}{(EA)_s^2} H_1 + \frac{P^* M_s^*}{(EA)_s D_s} H_2 + \frac{M_s^{*2}}{D_s^2} H_3 \right) \quad (3)$$

where

$$P^* = C_2 M_b \quad (4a)$$

$$M_d^* = M_d - C_3 M_b \quad (4b)$$

$$M_s^* = P^* \left(e_s + \frac{h_c}{2} + \frac{h_{f1}}{2} \right) - M_d^* \quad (4c)$$

where, C_2 and C_3 and H_1 , H_2 and H_3 are provided in Appendix. h_c and h_{f1} are the core and upper face thicknesses. ν_{f1} in Eq. (3) is Poisson’s ratio of the upper face. E_{f1} is the upper face modulus, and $(EA)_s$ is axial stiffness of the lower cracked region in Fig. 1 given by,

$$(EA)_s = E_c h_c + E_{f2} h_{f2} \quad (5)$$

where E_c and E_{f2} are the moduli of the core and lower face, and h_{f2} is the thickness of the lower face.

D_d is the flexural stiffness of the upper face (per unit width),

$$D_d = E_{f1} \frac{h_{f1}^3}{12} \quad (6)$$

D_s is the flexural stiffness of the cracked region below the debond plane (per unit width),

$$D_s = E_c \frac{h_c^3}{12} + E_c h_c e_s^2 + E_{f2} \frac{h_{f2}^3}{12} + E_{f2} h_{f2} \left(\frac{h_{f2}}{2} + \frac{h_c}{2} - e_s \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

where distance e_s (Fig. 1) is given by

$$e_s = \frac{E_{f2} h_{f2} \left(\frac{h_{f2}}{2} + \frac{h_c}{2} \right)}{(EA)_s} \quad (8)$$

The complex stress intensity factor K_1 and K_2 are defined by [8,9],

$$K = K_1 + iK_2 \quad (9)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

In our previous publication [6], the stress intensity factors were derived based on the relation between the energy release rate and the square of the magnitude of K

$$|K| = (K_1^2 + K_2^2)^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

This led to the following expression,

$$K = K_1 + iK_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{B}} \left(-P^* \sqrt{a_1} - i e^{i\gamma} M_d^* \sqrt{a_2} \right) h_{f1}^{-i\epsilon} e^{i\omega} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\sin \gamma = \frac{a_3}{2\sqrt{a_1 a_2}} \quad (12a)$$

$$B = \frac{G_c (\kappa_{f1} + 1) + G_{f1} (\kappa_c + 1)}{16G_{f1} G_c \cosh^2 \pi \epsilon} \quad (12b)$$

$$\kappa_{f1} = 3 - 4\nu_{f1} \quad (12c)$$

$$\kappa_c = 3 - 4\nu_c \quad (12d)$$

(both for plane strain)

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{2\pi} \ln \frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta} \quad (12e)$$

$$\beta = \frac{G_{f1} (\kappa_c - 1) - G_c (\kappa_{f1} - 1)}{G_{f1} (\kappa_c + 1) + G_c (\kappa_{f1} + 1)} \quad (12f)$$

G_{f1} and G_c are the shear moduli of the upper face and core. The parameter ω in Eq. (11) acts similar to a phase angle and depends only on the combination of materials and the thickness of the face sheets and core, but not on the loading. Based on expression (11) it is possible to define the mode-mixity phase angle, ψ , following Hutchinson et al. [8] and Rice [9], see also Fig. 4,

$$\psi = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{\lambda \sin \omega - \cos(\omega + \gamma)}{\lambda \cos \omega + \sin(\omega + \gamma)} \right] \quad (13a)$$

$$\lambda = -\frac{P^*}{M_d^*} \sqrt{\frac{a_1}{a_2}} \quad (13b)$$

Notice here that the oscillation is suppressed, because,

$$K h_{f1}^{i\epsilon} = |K| e^{i\psi} \quad (14)$$

Mode-mixity analysis of the DCB-UBM specimen

The DCB-UBM specimen shown in Fig. 2 with specific face and core material properties and dimensions is analyzed here. The objective of the analysis is to examine two typical symmetric sandwich specimen with 2 mm thick aluminum face sheets ($h_{f1}=h_{f2}=h_f=2$ mm and $E_{f1}=E_{f2}=E_f=70$ GPa) and a 20 mm thick core ($h_c=20$ mm). ‘‘Stiff’’ ($E_c=7$

GPa) and “soft” ($E_c=130$ MPa) core materials were considered. The two core materials produced respectively “moderate” mismatch ($E_f/E_c=10$) and “large” mismatch ($E_f/E_c=538$) between face and core stiffnesses.

These sandwich specimens were analyzed using 2D plane strain finite element analysis in Ref. [6]. This analysis verified the invariance of the parameter ω with loading, and provided the results listed in Table I. Based on the values of ω listed in Table I it is possible to analyze the mode-mixity for sandwich specimens with the face and core combinations and thicknesses specified above for a large range of DCB-UBM loadings.

The DCB-UBM specimen is loaded by two end moments as illustrated in Figs. 2 and 3. A range of mixed mode loadings may be achieved by testing specimens with various moments M_s and M_d . Hence, a single parameter expressing the loading is the moment ratio; M_d/M_s .

Fig. 5 shows the results for the two types of sandwich DCB-UBM specimens obtained from this analysis. When the moments act in opposite directions, $M_d/M_s < 0$, the crack will open. For the sandwich specimen with soft core (H100), the phase angle is close to zero at a moment ratio of -1, which would correspond to mode I dominated loading. When the moment ratio increases towards zero, the phase angle increases and approaches 90° , which corresponds to positive mode II dominated loading. When the moment ratio changes sign, the mode-mixity angle transits from values close to 90° to values close to -90° , i.e. negative mode II dominated loading. For this case, however, crack face contact may occur which would invalidate the quantitative results. For larger values of the moment ratio, the phase angle increases and approaches values close to -30° . It is noted that mode-mixity angles between about -30° and 0° are not achievable for this test specimen. We will examine if asymmetric sandwich beams would cover this range of mode-mixities in a future publication. For the sandwich specimen with a stiff core and a moment ratio of -1, the phase angle is about -30° . If the ratio is increased towards 0, the phase angle remains nearly constant, but increases rapidly towards 90° , when M_d/M_s approaches zero from the negative side. The phase angle transitions to values close to -90° at very small positive moment ratios and then increases

rapidly with M_d/M_s to reach an angle of about -30° asymptotically. Thus, for the case of a stiff core, the DCB-UBM test produces the full range of mode-mixities, although issues such as crack face contact must be examined more closely. Furthermore, the phase angle is highly sensitive to small changes of the moment ratio.

Concluding Remarks

The mode-mixity of debonded sandwich DCB-UBM specimens has been examined using a closed-form analysis. This analysis provides the energy release rate and the stress intensity factors in terms of a single scalar quantity, ω , which is independent of the loading of the specimen. Thus, ω can be extracted for specific sandwich beam configurations using finite element analysis of just one loading configuration. Analysis of debonded sandwich specimens with “soft” and “stiff” foam cores revealed that crack tip loading can be achieved using the DCB-UBM specimen over a large range of mode-mixity phase angles, although a range (“gap”) in mode-mixities was found for the specimen with a soft core. Methods to remedy the situation will be examined, such as using asymmetric sandwich specimens.

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Appendix

Parameters for fracture analysis of debonded DCB-UBM sandwich beam specimens

$$C_2 = \frac{E_{f1}h_{f1}}{2D_b}(2e_b + h_{f1} + h_c),$$

$$C_3 = \frac{E_{f1}}{D_b} \frac{h_{f1}^3}{12} \quad (A1.a,b)$$

$$e_b = \frac{E_{f2}h_{f2}\left(\frac{h_{f2}}{2} + \frac{h_c}{2}\right) - E_{f1}h_{f1}\left(\frac{h_{f1}}{2} + \frac{h_c}{2}\right)}{E_{f1}h_{f1} + E_ch_c + E_{f2}h_{f2}} \quad (A2)$$

$$D_b = E_{f1} \frac{h_{f1}^3}{12} + E_{f1}h_{f1} \left(\frac{h_{f1}}{2} + \frac{h_c}{2} + e_b \right)^2 + E_{f2} \frac{h_{f2}^3}{12} + E_{f2}h_{f2} \left(\frac{h_{f2}}{2} + \frac{h_c}{2} - e_b \right)^2 + E_c \frac{h_c^3}{12} + E_ch_c e_b^2 \quad (A3)$$

$$H_1 = \frac{1-v_c^2}{2} E_ch_c + \frac{1-v_{f2}^2}{2} E_{f2}h_{f2} \quad (A4.a)$$

$$H_2 = \frac{1-v_c^2}{2} E_ch_c 2e_s + \frac{1-v_{f2}^2}{2} E_{f2}h_{f2} (2e_s - h_c - h_{f2}) \quad (A4.b)$$

$$H_3 = \frac{1-v_c^2}{2} E_ch_c \left(\frac{h_c^2}{12} + e_s^2 \right) + \frac{1-v_{f2}^2}{2} E_{f2}h_{f2} \left[\frac{h_{f2}^2}{3} + \left(\frac{h_c}{2} - e_s \right) \left(\frac{h_c}{2} + h_{f2} - e_s \right) \right] \quad (A4.c)$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(1-v_{f1}^2)}{2E_{f1}h_{f1}} + \frac{H_1}{(EA)_s^2} + \frac{H_2}{(EA)_s D_s} \left(e_s + \frac{h_c}{2} + \frac{h_{f1}}{2} \right) + \frac{H_3}{D_s^2} \left(e_s + \frac{h_c}{2} + \frac{h_{f1}}{2} \right)^2 \quad (A5.a)$$

$$a_2 = (1-v_{f1}^2) \frac{E_{f1}h_{f1}^3}{24D_d^2} + \frac{H_3}{D_s^2} \quad (A5.b)$$

$$a_3 = \frac{H_2}{(EA)_s D_s} + 2 \frac{H_3}{D_s^2} \left(e_s + \frac{h_c}{2} + \frac{h_{f1}}{2} \right) \quad (A5.c)$$

Tables and Figures

Table 1. Parameter ω for sandwich specimens with “soft” and “stiff” cores [6]. $E_f=70$ GPa, $\nu_f=0.32$, $\nu_c=0.32$.

E_c , MPa	ω , deg.
7	57.2±2.4
130	73.7±0.4

Figure 3. Moments acting on an element of a DCB-UBM sandwich specimen containing a debond crack at the face/core interface.

Figure 1. Forces and moments acting on an element of a sandwich beam containing a debond crack at the face/core interface.

Figure 4. Definition of the mode-mixity phase angle, ψ , following Hutchinson et al. [8] and Rice [9].

Figure 2. Basic principle of the DCB-UBM test method.

Figure 5. Results for the two types of sandwich DCB-UBM specimens with “soft” (H100) and “stiff” (Alum Foam) cores obtained from analysis. $h_f=2$ mm, $h_c=20$ mm.